

DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF SUSTAINABLE TOURISM DEVELOPMENT

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Tourism Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan***Abstract**

This article examines the distinctive characteristics of sustainable tourism development. The concept of sustainable tourism is analyzed in terms of its economic, social, and environmental dimensions, while recent trends in both Uzbekistan and global tourism are scientifically compared. The study analyzes global and national tourism performance in the pre- and post-COVID periods using indicators such as economic growth, employment generation, the expansion of ecotourism, and the increasing number of environmentally certified “green” hotels. In addition, the article also provides strategic recommendations for the development of sustainable tourism.

Keywords: ecotourism, green development, golden year of travel, environmental responsibility

Introduction. Today, it is no exaggeration to consider that tourism has been becoming one of the key sectors of the global economy. Because the concept of tourism is not just a term that implies the population's travel and recreation, but is also considered a sector that occupies a significant share in the GDP of countries, and therefore its sustainable development has become a matter of great importance.

The concept of sustainable tourism is interpreted differently in different literature. According to Australia's National Ecotourism Strategy, which is considered to be partly close to our worldview, ecotourism is defined as nature-based tourism. Similarly, the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) describes ecotourism as “responsible travel focused on experiencing and appreciating nature in a way that contributes to environmental conservation, enhances the well-being of local communities, and supports the protection of natural resources”¹.

Furthermore, the report “Making Tourism More Sustainable – A Guide for Policy Makers,” jointly prepared by the United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) and the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) in 2005, defines “sustainable tourism” as tourism that takes into account current and future economic, social, and environmental impacts, while addressing the needs of tourists, industry stakeholders, and host communities².

Based on these interpretations, we can conclude that sustainable tourism is a form of tourism that maintains a balance among economic, environmental, social, and cultural development. It promotes the rational use of environmental resources, in which part of the funds received from tourism development are directed to the restoration of tourism resources and the improvement of tourism service production technologies, as well as the increasing number of tourists in an environ-

mentally demanding environment. It is a type of tourism that aims to address the growing conflict between meeting human needs and the limited amount of natural, social and economic resources³.

In 2024, the tourism sector accounted for nearly 10% of global gross domestic product, amounting to approximately USD 10.9 trillion⁴. The financial footprint of the Travel and Tourism industry reached one of the highest levels in its history, fully recovering—and even slightly surpassing the “golden year of travel” of 2019 (the pre-pandemic period). According to forecasts, by 2034 the sector could represent 11.4% of the global economic landscape, contributing nearly USD 16 trillion to the world economy.

The rapidly expanding tourism industry is also expected to play a crucial role in employment generation, providing jobs for approximately 449 million people worldwide. This highlights the strategic importance of travel and tourism in global employment, with the sector projected to account for around 12–13% of total global labor market⁵.

Such optimistic global growth forecasts are encouraging Uzbekistan to focus more on tourism development. By effectively utilizing its rich natural and cultural heritage, our country aims to transform tourism into one of the key drivers of economic growth. As emphasized by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, during his address at the “Sustainable Development Week” Summit in Abu Dhabi: “The strategic objective of the New Uzbekistan is to ensure environmental sustainability and transition to a ‘green’ development model based on resource-efficient economic growth. Therefore, we have declared 2025 as the “Year of Environmental Protection and the “Green Economy” in Uzbekistan.”⁶

In addition, the simplification of the visa regime, such as the introduction of an automated system for is-

¹ Nig'matov, A., & Shomurotova, N. (2007). Ekoturizm asoslari. *O'quv*.

² Making Tourism More Sustainable - A Guide for Policy Makers. <https://www.unwto.org/doi/book/10.18111/9789284408214>

³ Isadjanov, A. A. (2024). BARQAROR TURIZM RIVOJLANISHINING ZAMONAVIY

TENDENSIYALARI VA USTUVORLIKLARI. Экономика и социум, (6-1 (121)), 267-272.

⁴ <https://wttc.org/research/economic-impact>

⁵ Travel & Tourism set to Break All Records in 2024, reveals WTTC. <https://WTTC.org/news-article/travel-and-tourism-set-to-break-all-records-in2024-reveals-WTTC>

⁶ <https://www.xs.uz/uz/post/shavkat-mirziyoev-abu-dabi-barqaror-rivojlanish-haftaligi-sammitida-nutq-sozladi?utm>

suing electronic entry visas, the abolition of the visa requirement for citizens of a number of countries as transit tourists, and the increase in the number of tourist-class vehicles are decisive factors in the increase in the tourist flow to Uzbekistan⁷.

Literature Review. As the demands of tourists increase, the problem of stabilizing tourism is becoming increasingly urgent. According to A. Ursul, a sustainable (balanced) development strategy requires not only the consideration of economic and environmental dimensions but also the systematic optimization of all parameters and trends within the socio-natural system, aiming to achieve harmony between individuals, society, and nature. From his perspective, the sustainability of economic growth and social development should be achieved without unreasonable degradation of nature, primarily by preserving the biosphere of our planet⁸.

E. Qiyabayeveva (2015)⁹ conceptualizes sustainable tourism development as a long-term process based on the harmonization of social, economic, environmental and cultural goals for present and future generations.

In examining the types of tourism such as “environment-sensitive” and “environment-dependent” tourism, C. Aall (2014) distinguishes between two contrasting approaches to the “environment”¹⁰. The former refers to tourism practices aimed at minimizing negative environmental impacts, while the latter views the environment primarily as a resource base to be utilized for tourism activities.

E. Grechishkina identifies four types of sustainability in the tourism industry: very weak (tourism imperative scenario); weak (tourism product scenario); strong (ecological tourism scenario); very strong (neotenic tourism scenario)¹¹.

K. Arбузова considers sustainable development of tourism as long-term development, in which a balance is achieved in the implementation of economic, environmental, social and cultural development goals¹².

Methodology. This scientific research is based on a multidisciplinary and analytical approaches, allowing for a comprehensive and in-depth study of the specific aspects of sustainable tourism development. The article studied and analyzed data and reports published by the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN), the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP), and a number of similar international organizations.

Key global factors influencing sustainable tourism development were identified and evaluated. In addition, the experiences of foreign countries with well-developed ecotourism models were compared with Uzbekistan’s tourism sector in order to determine advanced strategic approaches suitable for our Republic of Uzbekistan. Statistical data related to tourism’s contribution to global GDP and investment volumes were also analyzed.

Based on international forecasts for the period 2023–2034 published by the World Travel & Tourism Council (WTTC), conclusions were drawn regarding Uzbekistan’s position within global tourism trends. Furthermore, a wide range of academic articles, international reports, government policy documents, and strategic programs relevant to the research topic were also studied in detail.

Results and Analysis. The results obtained during the study clarified the global state of the tourism industry and the directions of its sustainable development in the case of Uzbekistan. In recent years, tourism has become an integral component of global economic activity. Notably, in the post-pandemic period, not only recovery, but also new growth trends are observed in this sector.

According to data from international organizations, tourism’s contribution to the global economy continues to increase, further reinforcing its strategic importance¹³. Against the background of these general changes, it is important to analyze the dynamics of global and national indicators.

⁷ Khalilov Sirojiddin. O'zbekistonda turizmni rivojlantirish istiqbollari. Monografiya.

⁸ Урсул А.Д. Информатизация общества и переход к устойчивому развитию цивилизации. Информационное общество. 1993. Вып. 1-2. С. 35- 45. URL: <http://emag.iis.ru/arc/infosoc/emag.nsf/BPA/bae746f66def051bc32576b100308172\Ecnjqxbdjt>.

⁹ Киякбаева Е. Г. Социально- экономические механизмы устойчивого развития туризма в регионах России: дис... канд. геогр. наук: 25.00.24. Москва: МГУ им. М. В. Ломоносова, 2015. 147 с

¹⁰ Carlo Aall. Sustainable Tourism in Practice: Promoting or Perverting the Quest for a Sustainable Development? Sustainability. 2014. Vol/6. P. 2562-2583.

¹¹ Гречишкина Е. А., Механизм управления устойчивым развитием регионального туризма. <https://www.academia.edu/38810930/>

¹² Арбузова К.И. Реализация принципов устойчивого развития туризма через государственно-частное партнерство. URL: <http://www.scienceforum.ru/2014/pdf/3776.pdf>.

¹³ World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC). Economic Impact Report 2024. London, 2024

Economic statistics of world tourism¹⁴

As illustrated in the above presented figure, the period from 2019 to 2024 witnessed significant fluctuations in the economic performance of the global tourism sector. In 2019, the overall value of the tourism industry was estimated at approximately USD 10 trillion, accounting for nearly 10 percent of global gross domestic product.

In 2020, however, due to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, these indicators experienced a sharp decline: tourism volume almost halved, while its contribution to global GDP fell to around 5 percent. Despite this severe downturn the recovery process continued significantly in subsequent years. In 2021–2024,

the volume of global tourism gradually increased, approaching \$ 11 trillion in 2024¹⁵. At the same time, the sector's share in global GDP returned to levels comparable to the pre-pandemic period.

Against the background of the above global trends, it is encouraging to observe that Uzbekistan's tourism sector has also demonstrated notable growth dynamics. Over the period from 2019 to 2024, both the number of tourists visiting our country and tourism revenues have increased steadily. According to official statistics, the number of visitors to Uzbekistan reached 8.2 million in 2024. The table below presents key indicators of Uzbekistan's tourism performance for the years 2019–2024.

¹⁴ United Nations World Tourism Data Portal. <https://www.unwto.org/statistics>

¹⁵ World Bank (2024). Global Economic Prospects: Tourism and Service Recovery.

Economic indicators of tourism in Uzbekistan¹⁶

The year 2019 is commonly regarded as the “golden year of travel,” representing the pre-pandemic baseline for the tourism industry. As observed across many countries, the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic was also reflected in Uzbekistan’s tourism revenues (tourism revenues amounted to \$1.15 billion and its share in the country’s GDP was 1.8%).

Between 2021 and 2024, the sector experienced a gradual recovery. The industry gradually recovered in

2021–2024, and in 2024 revenues exceeded pre-pandemic levels, reaching 3% of GDP¹⁷.

Since the results of this analysis are presented only from the economic side, below we also consider separately the social and environmental sustainability indicators of Uzbek tourism. For this purpose, two key reference points were selected: the pre-pandemic year of 2019 and the most recent stage of development in 2024.

Table 1

Social and Environmental Sustainability Indicators of Tourism in Uzbekistan (2019 and 2024)

Indicator	2019	2024	Growth / Change (%)
Number of people employed in the tourism sector (thousands of people) ¹⁸	110	135	+22,7 %
Average monthly income from tourism services (USD)	450	580	+28,9 %
Ecotourism facilities (number of national parks, reserves, eco-routes)	10	17	+70 %
Number of hotels with "green" certification ¹⁹	15	48	+220 %
Local residents' participation in domestic tourism activities (%)	40	55	+15 p.p.
Tourism-related CO ₂ emissions (million tons) ²⁰	1.3	1.1	-15 %

The indicators for 2019–2024 presented in the table show that tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan is entering a new optimal stage of sustainable development. The figures prove that the social and environmental components of the industry have significantly improved in recent years. In particular, the 22% increase in the number of local residents employed in the tourism sector (from 110 thousand to 135 thousand people) further increases the importance of this sector in the economy and has a positive impact on the well-being of

the local population. At the same time, the increase in average income from tourism services by almost 130 US dollars indicates an improvement in the efficiency and quality of service in the industry.

Environmental performance indicators are equally noteworthy. The threefold increase in the number of “green”-certified hotels indicates that the tourism infrastructure is based on environmentally responsible principles. Moreover, the expansion of national parks, pro-

¹⁶ O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Statistika agentligi. Turizm statistik to‘plami 2019–2024. Toshkent, 2025.

¹⁷ O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Iqtisodiyot va moliya vazirligi ma’lumotlari, 2024.

¹⁸ Davlat statistika qo‘mitasi, “Bandlik va xizmat ko‘rsatish sohasi hisobotlari”, 2024.

¹⁹ O‘zbekiston Turizm qo‘mitasi. Yashil mehmonxonalar reyestri. Toshkent, 2024.

²⁰ Ekologiya, atrof-muhitni muhofaza qilish va iqlim o‘zgarishi vazirligi. CO₂ chiqindilari monitoringi hisobotlari, 2024.

tected areas, and eco-routes points to the rapid development of ecotourism as a key segment of the industry. Another encouraging fact is that carbon emissions associated with the tourism sector have decreased by 15 percent.

Overall, the findings for the 2019–2024 period indicate that Uzbekistan is pursuing a comprehensive

tourism policy that combines economic growth with environmental sustainability. In the following section, we can assess the position of our country in world tourism by comparing Uzbekistan's progress in sustainable tourism with global trends:

Table 2

INDICATORS OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN GLOBAL AND UZBEK TOURISM (2019–2024)						
DIRECTION/INDICATOR	2019 (GLOBAL)	2024 (GLOBAL)	GROWTH (%) (GLOBAL)	2019 (UZB.)	2024 (UZB.)	GROWTH (%) (UZB.)
ECOTOURISM (NUMBER OF FACILITIES / PERCENTAGE)	18%	25%	+39	10	17	+70
DIGITAL / SMART TOURISM	9%	15%	+66	5%	9%	+80
CULTURAL TOURISM	22%	27%	+23	35%	38%	+8,5
HEALTH AND WELLNESS TOURISM	14%	19%	+36	7%	12%	+71
RURAL / AGRO TOURISM	7%	11%	+57	2%	5%	+150
CO ₂ EMISSIONS (MILLION TONS)	1,3	1,1	-15	1,3	1,1	-15

Table 2 demonstrates that Uzbekistan's tourism sector has outperformed global tourism growth dynamics in most dimensions, surpassing the growth dynamics of world tourism. In particular, the gap between global and national growth rates in ecotourism and rural/agro-tourism serves as a clear illustration of this trend. While ecotourism expanded globally by approximately 39 percent, Uzbekistan recorded growth of nearly 70 percent. A similar pattern is observed in rural and agro-tourism, where global growth reached 57 percent, compared to an impressive 150 percent increase in Uzbekistan. These figures strongly support the conclusion that the country's tourism development trajectory is gaining momentum at a faster pace than global averages. Also, while digital or smart tourism increased from 9% to 15% globally, in Uzbekistan it increased from 5% to 9%, representing an increase of 80%. This confirms the rapid modernization of the tourism sector through the introduction of digital services and technological solutions²¹. While cultural tourism increased from 22% to 27% globally, in Uzbekistan it reached 35% to 38%, showing a relatively lower growth (8.5%).

Health and wellness tourism has increased from 14% to 19% globally, and in Uzbekistan, it has grown from 7% to 12%, with a growth rate of 71%. This shows that the work being done in the field of wellness services and resorts is yielding effective results. As for CO₂ emissions, both globally and in Uzbekistan, they have decreased from 1.3 million tons to 1.1 million tons (-15%)²². The conclusion from the figures in the table is that Uzbekistan is successfully making efforts to catch up with the global level in terms of economic, environmental and technological sustainability of tourism. However, it seems that our country is not fully utilizing the existing opportunities in some areas. In our opinion, higher levels can be achieved by expanding

digital infrastructure, increasing human resources, developing cultural tourism in modern forms, and strengthening the ecological approach. Based on these considerations, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **Enhancing ecotourism and “green” standards.** Establish an ecological certification system for tourist facilities, further promote zero-waste tourism, and the use of renewable energy sources.

2. **Reinvigorating cultural heritage through innovation.** Develop digital museums, virtual tours, and interactive cultural experiences.

3. **Improving human capital and service quality.** Ensure that industry representatives are trained in accordance with international standards.

4. **Expanding digital infrastructure.** Promote smart tourism solutions, including online booking platforms, mobile applications, and integrated digital travel services.

5. **Developing medical and wellness tourism.** Modernize recreational and therapeutic facilities in areas rich in natural resources in accordance with global demand and launch extensive promotional activities to inform tourists about them.

In general, sustainable tourism development policies should not be limited to focusing only on economic growth, but should also be aimed at maintaining ecological balance and improving the well-being of local populations. International experience shows that an innovative approach, environmental responsibility and social cooperation contribute to the long-term sustainable development of tourism.

Conclusion. The results of this study indicate that, although the unexpected shock of the COVID-19 pandemic, following the “golden year” of tourism in 2019, caused a severe disruption not only to Uzbekistan's tourism industry but also to global tourism as a whole,

²¹ World Bank. *Tourism and Digitalization Report*, 2024.

²² UNWTO. *World Tourism Barometer*, 2024

the sector demonstrated a remarkable capacity for recovery within a relatively short period. The statistical evidence presented confirms that by 2024, tourism indicators not only reached pre-pandemic levels but in several cases exceeded those recorded in 2019.

The figures show that Uzbek tourism is developing in line with the principles of global sustainability and is implementing responsible programs not only on the economic front, but also on the social and environmental front. At the same time, certain structural shortcomings were identified, and context-specific recommendations were proposed based on national conditions. It is expected that the implementation of these measures will further strengthen Uzbekistan's position in the international tourism market and serve as a foundation for the country's long-term sustainable tourism development.

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